

YOUNG WOMEN'S RIGHTS AND EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6529194>

Mavlanova Sitora Sheraliyevna

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek Faculty of History.

Master's degree Management of State and Civil Society Institutions

Abstract: *This article supports the aspirations of young women for education, given that the development of society in today's era of globalization is directly related to the participation of young women with high scientific potential, the importance of the role of young women in science, strengthening the mechanism for the protection and implementation of their rights in this area, as well as the challenges facing the education of young women around the world. The author also cites a number of international declarations and conventions on women's rights adopted by the United Nations.*

Keywords: *UN, globalization, society, law, declaration, convention, discrimination, science, intellectual potential, legal consciousness, legal culture, creativity, spirituality, education, scientific worldview.*

Аннотация: *в данной статье поддерживаются стремления молодых женщин к образованию, учитывая, что развитие общества в современную эпоху глобализации напрямую связано с участием молодых женщин с высоким научным потенциалом, важностью роли молодых женщин в науке. укрепление механизма защиты и реализации своих прав в этой сфере, а также задачи, стоящие перед образованием молодых женщин во всем мире. Автор также цитирует ряд международных деклараций и конвенций о правах женщин, принятых ООН.*

Ключевые слова: *ООН, глобализация, общество, право, декларация, конвенция, дискриминационная наука, интеллектуальный потенциал, правосознание, правовая культура, творчество, духовность, образование, научное мировоззрение.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada bugungi globallashuv zamonida jamiyat rivoji ilmiy salohiyati yuqori yosh ayol-qizlar ishtiroki bilan bevosita bog'liqligi, yosh ayol-qizlarning ilm-fan sohasida tutgan o'rnining muhimligidan kelib chiqqan holda yosh ayol-qizlarning ta'lim olishga doir intilishlarini qo'llab-quvvatlash, bu boradagi huquqlarini muhofaza qilish va amalga oshirish mexanizimini mustahkamlash hamda butun dunyoda yosh ayol-qizlarning ta'lim olishi borasida yuzaga kelayotgan muammolar imkon qadar yoritib berilgan. Shuningdek, muallif maqolada Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti tomonidan ayol-qizlar huquqlariga doir qabul qilingan bir qancha xalqaro deklaratsiya va konvensiyalarni ham keltirib o'tgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *BMT, globallashuv, jamiyat, huquq, deklaratsiya, konventsiya, diskriminatsiya ilm-fan, intellektual salohiyat, huquqiy ong, huquqiy madaniyat, kreativlik, ma'naviyat, ta'lim-tarbiya, ilmiy dunyoqarash.*

In the current era of globalization, protecting the rights of young women to education, protecting their legitimate interests, and preventing violence against women are becoming increasingly important. The issue is also receiving international attention. Because today it is more important than ever to strengthen the role of women and girls in society, to protect their interests, to prevent violence against women and girls, and to achieve family stability. Although many international documents have been adopted, according to the United Nations, the number of deaths of young women and girls is still high worldwide. Millions of women live under physical violence. Her husband in his family perpetrates most of this violence. Violence and discrimination have increased during the pandemic. The world community as a negative situation that hinders the full physical, mental and psychological development of not only women but also their children interprets this situation. Legal protection of their aspirations to acquire lim is recognized as a topical issue today.

Since the middle of the twentieth century, the issue of the rights and freedoms of young women has become one of the most deeply troubling issues in the world. The most vulnerable and helpless part of society are women and girls. They suffer from discrimination and cruel treatment because of their weakness, because their legal rights are not fully respected, secured or unaware of their rights everywhere. Until the middle of the twentieth century, they were exploited against their will and human dignity. The course of social development shows that as life progresses, many things change. However, the treatment of young women was an exception. In the twentieth century, at a time when the global movement for human rights is gaining momentum, the issue of protecting the rights of women and girls, the most vulnerable and needy part of society, has also become relevant. "Women's rights are viewed more in terms of human needs than human rights".¹

In order to prevent such negative situations, the member states of the World Partnership have adopted a number of international legal instruments in the field of women and mothers' rights, which guarantee the rights of women and girls. Noda created a system of guaranteed sources of legal protection for young women and mothers. However, these sources did not come into being by themselves. These sources emerged in response to the fact that women and girls were not

¹ Чыж Эльжбета. Права ребенка. Хельсинкский фонд по правам человека, 2003. – В.: -С. 5.

recognized as independent individuals, and that their legal status was discriminated against in various spheres of social life. The existence of such events testifies to the legitimacy of the emergence and development of current sources in the field of women's rights. With the recognition of women's rights, there is a strong need to strengthen, ensure and protect them, and to give them legal force to take appropriate action. With the establishment of the United Nations in 1945, a new era began in the field of human rights, in particular the protection of women and girls' rights. Because this organization is an international, universal organization in the world. He considers it his priority to fight all the problems that exist in the world and to preserve the peace and security of humankind. The United Nations is concerned about the plight of young women around the world and has made it a priority to provide them with legal and other assistance. According to the United Nations, millions of women around the world are at risk of physical violence. Women not only become disabled because of brutal violence, they even die. Violence against women was assessed as an "extreme deviation" that negatively affected women's physical, psychological, and socioeconomic development.

Given the diversity of sources on women's rights, we list only the main sources:

1. International Bill of Human Rights, 1948 y.;
2. Geneva Convention on the Protection of Motherhood, 1952 y.;
3. Convention on the Political Rights of Women, 1952y.;
4. Convention on the Citizenship of Married Women, 1957 y.;
5. Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages, 1961 y.;
6. Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, 1967 y.;
7. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, 1979 y.;
8. Convention on the minimum age for employment, 1973 y.;
9. Declaration on the Protection of Women and Children during Emergencies and Military Conflicts, 1974 y.;
10. Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, 1984 y.;
11. Declaration against Torture of Women, 1993y
12. Additional Protocol on Child Trafficking, Child Prostitution and Pornography, 2002 y.

These sources are an incomplete list of legal sources regulating the rights and freedoms of women and girls. The pace of resource development is such that the process of constantly replenishing their ranks with new sources continues.

As human rights have become universal, the urgency of legal protection for young women has become particularly acute. Creating a culture of young women's rights in the whole system of society, cultivating respect for them, and achieving respect for them as an independent, full-fledged person has been identified as an important task.² The above-mentioned conventions and declarations have been adopted as the legal basis for the implementation of these tasks.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights is a universal document guaranteeing human rights. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights was adopted and promulgated on December 10, 1948, by UN General Assembly Directive 217. The declaration consists of 30 articles. The United Nations called on all peoples and nations to view this declaration as a duty to promote respect for the rights and freedoms set forth in the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. Article 16 of the Declaration of the Equality of Women and Men in Marriage states that "Adult men and women have the right to marry and to be married without any restrictions on race, nationality or religion. They have the same rights in marriage, in marriage and in divorce. Marriage may be entered into only with the free and full consent of the intending spouses. The family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection by society and the State". The ultimate goal of the inclusion of this article in the Declaration was to protect the rights of women and girls, restore their violated rights and equalize them in all respects. In the first quarter of the twentieth century, the escalation of violence against women, the violation of their rights, the escalation of cruelty to them, and their illegal exploitation forced the world community to pay serious attention to this problem. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights was also the first step in the development of legislation in this area.

International guarantees for the legal protection of women and girls include international instruments on the international legal protection of women's rights and freedoms and international mechanisms for the protection of women's rights.

The important stages of the women's movement are:

Declaration of 1975 as the First World Women's Conference and International Women's year (Mexico, Mexico);

² Bendas T.V. Gender psychology. Peter, 2006. -M.: - P. 26-28

1976-1985 UN Declaration of the 10th Anniversary of Women under the slogan "Equality, Development, Peace";

1980 II World Women's Conference (Copenhagen, Denmark);

1985 III World Women's Conference (Nairobi, Kenya);

1995 IV World Conference on the Status of Women (China, Beijing), Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action;

The 10th Anniversary of Human Rights Education at the 49th Session of the UN General Assembly, 1995-2004.

Today, the most important issues in the legal protection of young women and motherhood and childhood by the international community are the protection of the rights of mothers and children, the consistent implementation of rights in practice, benefits for pregnant women, reproductive health and gender equality are focusing on the issue. Achieving gender equality is a priority for international organizations such as the United Nations, UNESCO, and UNICEF. UNICEF and UNESCO are the world's leading international organizations for the protection of motherhood and childhood.

Although many documents on the rights of women and girls and mothers and children have been adopted, in some countries education and access to safe drinking water are still a dream. Today, 100 million children around the world are deprived of their dignity, freedom, future and childhood. The International Labor Organization estimates that 218 million children are employed worldwide.³ These children are deprived of the opportunity to go to school, play with friends or eat well and live a healthy and fulfilling life. 1.7 billion children are affected by violence globally each year. In the least developed countries, girls get married before the age of 18. 450 million children live in conflict-affected areas. In Brazil, more than 2 million children aged 5-14 are used as labor. In New Guinea, one in three children does not finish school. In Somalia, one in seven people under the age of five is malnourished. In Laos and Cambodia, more than a third of first-graders do not reach 5th grade. More than 12 million children are in forced labor in India. There are 300,000 child soldiers around the world. Early marriage of girls is common in Bangladesh. Even girls as young as 10 are forced to get married. In addition, for some as a baby gets older, he or she will outgrow this. As sad as the above is, this is the current picture of the world.

Legal protections for young girls need to be strengthened to put an end to such cases. That is, it is necessary to strengthen the legal framework for the

³ World Vision. Child Rights: History, Facts and How To Protect Them.

protection of the rights of young women to education, to ensure the implementation of laws and decisions in practice.

The international community has also introduced additional benefits for the education of mothers of young children or pregnant women in order to expand the legal protection of women and men. In this way, a pregnant woman or a mother with a young child can easily enjoy the opportunity to receive education at the same time as caring for the child. Special privileges are provided to mothers of young children to enter higher education institutions, because of which it is planned to create favorable conditions for women in family and social relations, to increase their participation in public life. In addition, I want to reiterate that being educated means believing in yourself, being interesting to those around you, to your family, and passing on your knowledge to the younger generation.

I am sure that every child - both boy and girl - comes to this world to be happy. We must respect their rights, and the rights are the same for everyone, regardless of the sex of the child. Every girl deserves a decent education and profession.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Фуко М. Воля. По ту сторону знания. Работы разных лет. Бурдье Начала, 2008. -М.: -С. 24.
2. Саипова К. Д. Реализации национальной политики среди национальных меньшинств Туркестана // Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe: Achievements and Perspectives. - 2015.
3. Хасбулатова О.А., Ушакова В.Г. Гендерные стереотипы в политической культуре: Специфика российского опыта // Женщина в российском обществе. 2013. -М.: №2
4. World Vision. Child Rights: History, Facts and How to Protect Them. 2018. - А.: -P. 11.
5. Helene Julien. Is There a Humane Right to Safe Motherhood with in the United Nations Legal System? // World Health Organization. 2014. - USA.: -P. 124.
6. Humanium. Historical overview of the children's rights evolution. 2019. - А.: -P. 14.
7. Information and communication technologies in education: UNESCO Institute for information technologies in education, 2013.
8. Bendas T.V. Gender psychology. Peter, 2006. -М.: - P. 26-28

9. Spike P.V. *Women's rights and society*. Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1992. -A.: -P. 225.
10. Connell R.W. *Gender and Power: Society, the person and Politics*. Cambridge, 2009. -A.: -P. 184.